

The role of leader to understand employee job issues: career development, work-place environment, employee satisfaction in context of leader-member exchange

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Abstract:

The fundamental purpose of this research is to understand the different job issues of employees in the context of leader-member exchange. These issues includes providing supportive environment to the employees by supervisor, employee selection decisions by management, compensation and benefit issues, career-development and promotion issues, job security issues, employee-empowerment and others. As well as this research also focus on the job needs of employees and their expectations from their supervisors and supervisors' expectations from their subordinates and to measure the employee's satisfaction from the job in context of all these issues. Qualitative approach has been used for the purpose of collecting data including survey and interviews and the respondents were the head of different departments and their subordinates who belongs to different universities and educational institutes of Sukkur region including Shah Abdul Latif University, institute of business administration Sukkur and Comsit Sukkur. The results indicates that if management will resolve issues of career development then quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates will enhance more than resolving issues of job satisfaction and workplace environment.

Introduction:

LMX refers to the worth of the relationship between leader and their subordinates. LMX theory focuses on the attributes of the leadership that is unnoticed by other leaders, which is divided in to two groups' in-group and out-group members. In- group is formed when there is high quality relationship between leader and their subordinates, means the relationship which is characterized by a high degree of mutual trust, understanding, respect and responsibility. At the other intense, out-group is there which is illustrated by low trust low level of responsibility, obligations and the lack of understanding.

LMX is an another way to understand the leaders' influence on their follower efficacy by focus on paired or dynamic relationship between the subordinates and the supervisor. Leader-Member Exchange model advocate that the supervisors do not employ the same behavior or same way consistently in dealing with all their subordinates or followers, but supervisor always use different style while dealing with their sub-ordinates. It depends on the performance of employees. Employees with out-standing performance are come are more close

to the supervisor and they in the category of in-group and employees with low performance also having low quality of relationship with their supervisor and they come in the category of out-group members

Literature review:

The current literature review determines the constructs along with the consequences of research that relates to the current study, which scrutinize the role of leader-member exchange in understanding the job issues, needs, obligations, expectations and employee satisfaction with the leader-ship.

Different scholars defined Leadership in massive number of ways. But the most frequently used leader-ship definitions engross the leader as an individual, the interaction process between the leader and their sub-ordinates and follower (Bass & B, 2008). The special effects of leader-ship behavior created on these cohesions, (G, p. 2013) systematized various kinds of approaches to leadership intense to "fifteen" different types of reasons for enhancing the understanding on leadership. (Stentz, Plano clerk, & Matkin, 2012) Used this model to categorize the leadership aspect

of the evaluated research articles since it characterized thorough summarized themes in the view of leadership areas approved in evidently distinguish-able categories

The largest part of the research on leadership come within reach of qualitative research technique as well as it residue for the most frequently used technique along with leader-ship researchers. Mix-method-designs are applied by many scholars in different fields of research as a mode to advanced theories. In order to explore and explicate the research-questions researchers used mix-method-designs for collecting as well analyzing data and adding the both qualitative and quantitative facts in sequence of research studies or in a single research. In the research (Stentz, Plano clerk, & Matkin, 2012) analyze the fundamental distinctiveness of mixed-method-designs. A wide range of leader-ship techniques offered to support how mixed-methods-design applications are put in to practice and wherever they might-be intended for future research projects.

(Dirks & Ferrin, 2002) Look at the allegations and findings of-the research on “trust-in- leadership” which has been conducted in earlier period. The study presents the estimation of most important relation-ships among trust-in-leadership and their key consequences. Subsequently, the research also discovers how to identify the constructs with another leadership (organizational leader-ship verse direct leader-ship/supervisor) and different kinds of trust fallout in analytically various relationships between the trust-in-leadership and their outcomes. Researcher used various kinds of methods to make sure that they had included accessible studies. Several interviews they conducted secondly researcher scrutinized the reference section of articles and books which provides description about the topic. At the end the researcher presents the theoretical frame-work to illuminate the different perceptions on building the trust-in-leadership.

(wayne, shore, & boomer) Scrutinized the-model-of the previous circumstances and the consequences of perceived-organizational-support in the context of leader-member exchange. Organizational performance provides appreciation to the human resource.

It was visualized that organizational integrity (distributive and ritual justice) and those practices of organization which provides feeling of inclusion and recognition to the workers/employees from top level management would manipulate the perceived-organizational-support.

It was expected that the punishment and reward behavior of a leader would be important predecessors for LMX. The domino effect of this research depend on a taster of 211 supervisor employees dyads specified that organizational recognition, enclosure and impartiality were associated to POS (perceived-organizational-support) along with deputation rewards were associated to LMX(Leader-member-exchange). At the end it was concluded that the POS is associated with assurance of employees and organizational-citizenship-behavior while performance-rating was predicted by LMX.

(Landry, 2009)Had been conducted survey from 240 people working in several different organizations. Author scrutinized the relation-ship among the supervisor` based self-esteem, commitment to the supervisor and leader-member-exchange as well as substantive-supervisor-sub-ordinate conflicts`. Research investigated that the affective-commitment is negatively relates to the both kinds of conflicts. When “SBSE” is low Affective-commitment is more strongly relates to both kinds of conflicts.

The leader-ship nature engrosses the use of power. (G., 2006) It can be illustrated as a multifaceted shape of performance which does not subsist except somewhat occurs (Mumford, 2011)

(M.S, 2007) Explore the relation-ship among “Leader-Member-Exchange” (LMX), job satisfaction, turnover intention and psycho-logical empowerment. The researcher conducted research in the perspective of` an up-scale, “limited-service restaurant` environment”. On-line survey has been conducted for this re-search Contributors in this research `responded in which these` things were gauged exploiting the LMX seven` (7) to gauge the eminence of t LMX `relationship and twelve` (12) objects to gauge the supposed altitude of psycho-

logical empowerment, questionnaires were developed to access turn-over intention and job-satisfaction. The results expose that the quality relationship of LMX and the intensity of psychological empowerment has considerable, direct linear relationships with the job-satisfaction.

Unexpectedly, job-satisfaction is not originated to contain statistically important relationship with turn-over intention as a whole for taster-group, whereas psycho-logical empowerment demonstrates to be most-reliable predictor of turn-over intention.

Research is typically based on following questions.

1. What kind of relationship is there between leader and their subordinates and what kind of relationship they are expected from each other in perspective of mutual trust and understanding?
2. What is the impact of career development issues on the relationship between leader and their subordinates?
3. What is the impact of employee satisfaction on the relationship between leader and their subordinates?
4. What is the impact of workplace environmental issues on the relationship between leader and their subordinates?

Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1:

Employee career development, employee job satisfaction, and work place environmental issues should be resolved for quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates.

Hypothesis 1A:

Employee career development issues should be resolved for managing quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates.

Hypothesis 1B:

Employee job satisfaction issues should be resolved for managing quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates.

Hypothesis 1C:

Workplace environmental issues should be resolved for management quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates.

Methodology:

For the current research qualitative data analysis approach has been used to data and the data has been analyzed and interpreted through Nvivo software. Data were collected in the form of interviews respondents were the heads of different departments and their subordinates belongs to different universities and educational institutes of Sukkur Region.

Results:

	Quality of exchange relationship
1. Employee career development issues	37.6%
2. Employee satisfaction issues	34.29%
3. Workplace environmental issues	28.11%

Results indicates that if management resolve issues of employee career development then quality of exchange relationship more enhance then resolving issues concern to employee satisfaction and work place environment.

Conclusion:

Using qualitative data from interview sources the study examined that due multiple changes occurring in the society employees have created great need for their career development. The quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates is depending upon career development of employees, employee satisfaction with the job and workplace environment. If management resolve all those issues related to career development of employees, employee satisfaction and workplace environment then quality of exchange relationship between leader and their subordinates will highly enhance.

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Appendix:

Text search and theme building query

Word frequency query

